

A spatial-temporal model to predict the amount of energy generated by solar vehicles

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Abstract: Solar-powered vehicles will be extensively used for transportation in near future with the development of the solar energy harvesting technology. However, there are certain aspects that need to be addressed to make solar-powered vehicles a reality, such as 'energy generation forecasting'. It is essential to forecast the amount of energy that can be generated during each journey in order to ensure the uninterrupted running of a solar-powered vehicle. Unfortunately, the existing energy generation forecasting methods have been developed for stationary solar panels, therefore, they cannot be used to forecast the amount of energy generated by a solar-powered vehicle. The Energy generation of a solar cell depends on 'spatial-temporal variables' that change rapidly. This study introduces a work-around to forecast the energy generated by solar-powered vehicles while they are on the move, and a computerized user interface to output the related information. All the factors for solar energy production were identified and real-time data was captured using the 'application programming interface (API)' services. It is a method that can be applied globally using route, terrain and weather data, while its accuracy has been tested on different routes, days, times, speeds, and precisions within a selected area in Sri Lanka using local route, terrain and weather data. The global application of the method achieves significant accuracy in a shorter computation time, while the local application achieves a similar accuracy in a comparatively longer computation time.

Keywords: solar vehicle; energy forecast; solar energy; energy production

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Introduction

With the depletion of nonrenewable energy resources, fossil energy in particular, and due to their contribution to climate change, renewable energy, such as solar and wind energy, is attracting focus. It has been predicted that the fossil fuel reserves, such as oil, gas, and coal will be exhausted by 2040, 2042, and 2112 respectively [1] Also, many researchers have discovered that the extensive burning of fossil fuels largely contributes to global warming [2], [3]. On the other hand, the contribution of renewable energy is not sufficient to meet the present global energy requirement, according to the 'International Energy Agency (IEA)' [4].

Transportation, one of the industries that consumes a large amount of energy globally, is mostly powered by fossil fuels that are vulnerable to both of the above threats. Solar energy has been suggested for the transportation industry many years ago and tested for more than a half century. Howard in 1960 invented a vehicle equipped with a 'solar steam

generator' that generates steam from solar energy which is used to power the vehicle [5]. Johnson in 1963 invented an aircraft powered by thermal energy generated by solar radiation which creates hot air passing through a ramjet to produce thrust [6]. He has calculated the magnitude of the radiation intensity depending on the location, time, date of the year, and weather conditions.

Bequerel in 1839 invented the 'photoelectric effect', the very principle of the solar cell, which converts solar radiation into electrical energy through materials [7]. As this concept has been identified as the best method for generating solar energy, it is currently used in household appliances, power plants, and vehicles that have been equipped with solar cells. Even though solar energy is widely harvested at stationary locations, such as households and power plants, it is hardly done in moving objects such as vehicles that have the same opportunity of being exposed to the sun. Therefore, solar-powered vehicles are rare compared to vehicles powered by fossil fuels and electricity. Uncertainty of energy generation and lack of efficient mechanisms to convert solar radiation to consumable energy are the main reasons for this phenomenon.

According to the latest reports, the maximum efficiency of a photovoltaic (PV) cell is 25% at the industrial level [8], [9] while it is 46% at the research level [10]. Although the efficiency of the solar cell has improved, the uncertainty of its energy generation still remains an issue. This has been addressed in this paper by introducing a dynamic, global model to estimate the power production of a solar-powered vehicle.

Forecasting solar irradiance, which is essential to forecast the output of a PV system, can be done using a number of different models introduced by many researchers. These models can be categorized as statistical, cloud imagery and satellite based, numerical weather prediction based, and hybrid [11]. Statistical methods are based on historical solar irradiance data. Mellit and Pavan in 2010 has introduced an artificial neural network (ANN) based method with an accuracy of 95% for 24 hour forecasting that uses mean daily solar irradiance and mean daily air temperature as inputs [12]. Another study conducted by Chen, Gooi, and Wang in 2013) that follows fuzzy and neural network based forecasting, uses past solar radiation data, sky conditions (sunny, rainy, or cloudy), and temperature as inputs [13]. The multivariate adaptive regression splines (MARS) forecasting method with more physical parameters, such as daily average, highest, and lowest temperatures, wind speed, duration of insolation, precipitation amount, humidity, dew temperature, and air pressure, has been used by Li et al. in 2016 [14]. Although these statistical methods that use historical data have shown higher success rates for static models, they cannot be applied to dynamic models, as it is not realistic to acquire historical data of every location on the earth.

Cloud imagery and satellite based models are used for short term predictions. Chow et al. in 2011 has used sunshine parameters and sky image to forecast cloud cover and solar irradiance for periods ranging from 30 seconds to 5 minutes with 60% accuracy [15]. Peng et al. in 2015 has achieved 26% improvement in all irradiance predictions compared to persistent models, using 3D cloud detection through multiple sky imagers to forecast for periods ranging from 1 minute to 15 minutes [16]. However, imagery and satellite based models are not viable for dynamic models as they are expensive and not frequently obtained.

Among all the methods that are currently used in forecasting solar irradiance at static locations, weather prediction based numerical methods are suitable for dynamic global models, Weather predictions depend on the location, date, and time. In the case of a solar-powered vehicle, these parameters should be computed using spatial-temporal methods, as they rapidly change.

According to the literature review it is evident that the methods available presently for predicting the solar energy generation have been developed based on the assumption that the solar cells are static, hence have constant latitudes and longitudes. Some of these methods have considered the systematic alignment variations of the solar cells. None of these methods are applicable for a solar-powered vehicle, due to the fact that the factors including the location and the alignment that determine the energy generation of a solar cell, fixed on such a vehicle, rapidly change while it is on the

move. The objective of this study is to develop a global model to forecast the energy generated by a solar-powered vehicle while it is on the move using spatial-temporal analyses.

The computation is carried out by considering the travel as a series of stops with small time intervals. The energy generation during each interval is computed by evaluating the solar intensity, incident angle, and temperature that is computed by evaluating the physical parameters, such as weather, time, and location. Aggregated energy generation of the series of stops defined for a given run is considered as the energy generation forecast for that run. Therefore, the proposed method can be considered as a 'physical method'. Accurate weather forecasts are not available for longer periods, hence the proposed method is limited to short-term predictions.

Following inputs are mandatory:

- a. Travelling from/ to;
- b. Starting date/ time;
- c. Expected average speed;
- d. Required precision;

With the above information, the instantaneous influences on the PV system at route segments are evaluated depending on the following factors:

- i. Location:
 - a. Latitude;
 - b. Longitude;
 - c. Elevation;
- ii. Time and date;
- iii. Weather (forecast):
 - a. Temperature;
 - b. Humidity;
 - c. Pressure;
 - d. Cloud cover (as a percentage);
- iv. Position of the sun:
 - a. Azimuth;
 - b. Zenith;
 - c. Declination;
 - d. Hour angle;
- v. Visibility of the sun;

Research Methodology

The model was developed for both selected and global extents. Data with high accuracy was used for the selected extent while data with low accuracy was used for the global extent. Route and terrain elevation data for the global model were captured through 'Bing Maps Routes API' and 'Bing Maps Elevation API' services while route and terrain elevation data for the model developed for the selected study area were captured through local survey data. Weather data was captured through 'Open Weather Map API' service for both extents.

Data retrieval, manipulation and calculation were done using a program which is written in 'Python' language. The program was further developed to include a 'toolbar' in 'ArcMap' using 'ESRI ArcGIS' add-in. The user can use the toolbar to input:

- Travelling from/ to (by selecting a city in a dropdown list, clicking map interface, or enter coordinates);
- Starting date/ time (by entering values);
- Expected average speed (by entering the value, or selecting one of the given values, i.e. '40 kmh⁻¹', '60 kmh⁻¹' or '80 kmh⁻¹');
- Required precision (by selecting among 'low', 'moderate', 'high', and very 'high')

2.1 Instantaneous location

The polyline of the closest route for a given journey is obtained using the route data with from/ to information provided by the user. Using the expected average speed ' V ' (ms⁻¹) and the required precision level ' P ' (s) (low – 300s, moderate – 60s, high – 10s, very high – 1s), the length of the instantaneous route segment ' L ' (m) is calculated using the equation 1.

$$\text{Equation 1 } L = V * P$$

The polyline is sectioned for each maximum length ' L ' from the beginning to the end. The terrain elevation at each node is obtained using the elevation data. Using the elevation at the start node ' h_1 ' and elevation at the end node ' h_2 ' of each segment, the gradient of the route segment ' M ' is computed using the equation 2.

$$\text{Equation 2 } M = (h_2 - h_1) / L$$

Using the coordinates (x_1, y_1) at the start and the coordinates (x_2, y_2) at the end of each route segment, the midpoint (x_M, y_M) is calculated using the equation 3.

$$\text{Equation 3 } (x_M, y_M) = [(x_1 + x_2) / 2, (y_1 + y_2) / 2]$$

The azimuth of travelling ' AZ ' is computed using the equation 4

$$\text{Equation 4 } AZ = \tan^{-1}[(x_2 - x_1) / (y_2 - y_1)] \text{ +/- Quadrant correction}$$

The estimated time at each midpoint is computed from the starting date/ time and the ' P '.

2.2 Weather

Weather information is captured for all the instantaneous locations at the estimated time using midpoints and time.

2.3 Sun's position

Using the instantaneous latitude, longitude, date and time as the inputs the sun azimuth, altitude, declination and hour angle are calculated instantaneously.

2.4 Solar irradiance

The effective solar irradiance on an inclined surface for cloudy sky ' I_E ' is computed by the following equations.

$$\text{Equation 5 } I_E = I_C * \cos Z$$

$$\text{Equation 6 } I_C = I_T * (1 - 0.72C^{3.2})$$

$$\text{Equation 7 } I_T = I_{Eff} + I_{Dif}$$

$$\text{Equation 8 } I_{Eff} = I_{Dir} \cos \alpha$$

$$\text{Equation 9 } I_{Dif} = I_R + I_A$$

$$\text{Equation 10 } I_{Dir} = I_0(T_0 T_R - A_W) T_A$$

$$\text{Equation 11 } I_R = I_0 T_0 (1 - T_R) / 2$$

$$\text{Equation 12 } I_A = I_0 (T_0 T_R - A_W) (1 - T_A) A_A G$$

Equation 13 $I_0 = I_s(1.00011 + 0.034221\cos\theta + 0.00128\sin\theta - 0.000719\cos2\theta + 0.000077\sin2\theta)$

Equation 14 $T_0 = 1 - A_0$

Equation 15 $T_R = 0.9768 - 0.0874M + 0.010607552M^2 - 0.000846205M^3 + 0.0000357246M^4 - 0.00000060176M^5$

Equation 16 $A_W = 0.29X_W / ((1+14.15X_W)^{0.635} + 0.5925X_W)$

Equation 17 $T_A = K_A^M (\cong 0.84^M)$

Equation 18 $G = 0.93 - 0.21 \ln(M)$

Equation 19 $A_0 = [0.1082X_0 / (1 + 13.86 X_0^{0.805})] + [0.00658X_0 / (1 + 10.36^3X_0^3)] + [0.00218 / (1 + 0.0042X_0 + 0.00000323X_0^2)]$

Equation 20 $M = M_{ST}[P(h) / P_{ST}(h)]$

Equation 21 $X_W = MU_W$

Equation 22 $X_0 = MU_0$

Equation 23 $M_{ST} = [\cos Z + 0.15 (93.885 - Z) - 1.253]^{-1}$

Equation 24 $P_{ST} = P_{ST}(h_0)[T(h)/T_{ST}(h_0)]^{5.2561}$

Equation 25 $U_W = 4.93U(h) * \exp(26.23 - 5416 / T(h)) / T(h)$

Equation 26 $T_{ST}(h_0) = T(h) + 0.0065h$

The parameters are listed in Table 1 with reference to the equations/ values with citations.

Symbol	Parameter	Equation/ Value	Citation
I_E	The effective solar irradiance on a inclined surface for cloudy sky	5	[17]
I_C	The total solar irradiance, perpendicular on sun rays for cloudy sky	6	[18]
Z	The zenith angle of the sun	Computation by inputs	
I_T	The total solar irradiance perpendicular on sun rays for cloudless sky	7	[19]
	Cloud percentage	Input by Weather API	
C	The fraction of the sky cloud cover	cloud percentage / 100	
I_{Eff}	The effective direct component of solar irradiance on an inclined surface	8	[19]
I_{Dif}	The diffuse component of solar irradiance	9	[20]
I_{Dir}	The direct component of solar irradiance on a horizontal surface	10	[19] * The surface elevation data and terrain elevation data are used to determine the visibility of the sun from the vehicle in the local model. If the visibility is no, $I_{Dir} = 0$, Otherwise I_{Dir} is computed.

α	The angle between the beam radiation on PV surface and the normal to that surface	27	
I_R	The diffuse irradiance on clear sky due to Rayleigh scattering	11	[19]
I_A	The diffuse irradiance on clear sky due to aerosol scattering	12	[19]
I_0	The extraterrestrial solar radiation perpendicular on sun rays	13	[19]
T_0	The transmissivity of the ozone layer	14	[19]
T_R	The the transmissivity of the atmosphere due to Rayleigh scattering by molecules	15	[18]
A_w	The absorptivity by water vapour	16	[19]
T_A	The transmissivity for aerosol	17	[19]
A_A	The spectrally averaged single scattering albedo for aerosols	0.75	[18]
G	The the ratio of forward to total scattering by aerosol	18	[19]
I_s	The solar constant	1366.1 Wm ⁻²	[19]
θ		$2\pi(n-1)/365$	
n	The date of the year	Input by User	
A_0	The absorption coefficient by the ozone layer	19	[19]
M	The air mass affected by correction	20	[19]
X_w	The length of the radiation path through the water precipitable layer	21	[19]
K_A	The unit air mass transmissivity	0.84	[19]
X_0	The length of the radiation path through the ozone layer	22	[19]
M_{ST}	The standard air mass	23	[21]
$P(h)$	The atmospheric pressure	Input by Weather API	
$P_{ST}(h)$	The standard atmospheric pressure at altitude h	24	[19]
U_w	The equivalent thickness of the precipitable water layer	25	[22]
U_0	The equivalent depth of the ozone layer in the atmosphere	3.5mm	[18]
$P_{ST}(h_0)$	The standard atmospheric pressure at the sea level	1017.085hP a	
$T(h)$	The temperature at altitude h	Input by Weather API	
$T_{ST}(h_0)$	The standard ambient temperature at the sea level	26	[23]
	Humidity percentage	Input by Weather API	
$U(h)$	The air relative humidity as a fraction at ground level	humidity/ 100	

Table 1 Parameter descriptions for equations 5-26

2.5 Model solar-powered vehicle

In order to forecast the energy generated by a solar-powered vehicle, the parameters related to the vehicle and the solar cells have to be known. Accordingly a model solar-powered vehicle, 'Sion' car model, produced by the 'Sono Motors GmbH, Munich, Germany, was selected with the following parameters:

Properties of the PV cells [9]

Mono-crystalline silicon cells (15cm x 15cm);

0.8 fill factor;

$C_s = 8977.5$ mA short circuit current at standard test conditions;

$V_s = 729$ mV open circuit voltage at standard test conditions;

$K = (-0.37\%)K^{-1}$ and $(0.04\%)K^{-1}$ temperature coefficients for open circuit voltage and close circuit current;

$T_s = 298.0$ K standard temperature;

$G_s = 1000$ Wm⁻² standard irradiance;

330 PV cells are on the surfaces with the following alignments:

136 cells on the rooftop (assume horizontal);

65 cells on the left (assume vertical and -90° azimuth from the travelling direction);

65 cells on the right (assume vertical and +90° azimuth from the travelling direction);

20 cells on the back (assume vertical and 180° azimuth from the travelling direction);

44 cells on the front (assume 30° slope and 0° azimuth);

Angle between the beam radiation on the PV surface and the normal to that surface ' α ' can be computed by using the equation 27 [17].

$$\text{Equation 27} \quad \cos \alpha = \sin \delta \sin \varphi \cos \beta - \sin \delta \cos \varphi \sin \beta \cos \gamma + \cos \delta \cos \varphi \cos \beta \cos \omega + \cos \delta \sin \varphi \sin \beta \cos \gamma \cos \omega + \delta \sin \beta \sin \gamma \sin \omega$$

Where:

δ is the declination of the sun;

φ is the latitude of the location;

β is the angle between the plane of the surface and the horizontal: $0^\circ \leq \beta \leq 180^\circ$. ($\beta > 90^\circ$ (the surface has a downward-facing component), β is evaluated by Equation 28;

γ is the deviation of the projection on a horizontal plane of the normal to the surface from the local meridian, with zero due south, east negative, and west positive: $-180^\circ \leq \gamma \leq 180^\circ$. γ is evaluated by Equation 29;

ω is the hour angle of the sun;

Slope angle ' β ' is computed with the alignment of the PV cell and the gradient ' M ' of the route segment. The slope angle is computed as follows with the assumption that there are only 5 different alignments of PV cells.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Equation 28} \quad & \text{For cells fixed on the rooftop:} & \beta &= |M|; \\ & \text{For cells fixed on sideways:} & \beta &= 90^\circ; \\ & \text{For cells fixed in the rear:} & \beta &= |M| + 90^\circ; \\ & \text{For cells fixed in the front:} & \beta &= |M| + 30^\circ; \end{aligned}$$

Azimuth angle ' γ ' is computed with the alignment of the PV cell and the azimuth of the travelling direction ' AZ ' of the route segment.

$$\text{Equation 29} \quad \text{For cells fixed on the rooftop:} \quad \gamma = AZ - 180^\circ;$$

- For cells fixed on the left side: $\text{if } AZ < 270^\circ, \gamma = AZ - 180^\circ, \text{ else; } \gamma = AZ - 450^\circ;$
- For cells fixed on the right side: $\text{if } AZ < 90^\circ, \gamma = AZ + 90^\circ, \text{ else; } \gamma = AZ - 270^\circ;$
- For cells fixed in the rear: $\text{if } AZ < 180^\circ, \gamma = AZ, \text{ else; } \gamma = AZ - 360^\circ;$
- For cells fixed in the front: $\gamma = AZ - 180^\circ;$

2.6 Output power

The maximum output power by a PV cell ‘P’ at each route segment can be computed by the following equations:

Equation 30 $P = I_{sc} * V_{oc} * FF;$

Equation 31 $I_{sc} = C_s I_E [1 + K(T(h) - T_s)] / G_s;$

Equation 32 $V_{oc} = V_s + K(T(h) - T_s);$

The parameters are listed in Table 2 with reference to the equations and values with citations.

Symbol	Parameter	Equation/ Value	Citation
<i>P</i>	The maximum output power by a PV cell	30	[24]
<i>I_{sc}</i>	The photocurrent generated at short circuit condition	31	[25]
<i>V_{oc}</i>	The ambient voltage created at open circuit conditions	32	[25], [26]

Table 2. Parameter descriptions for equations 30-32

2.7 Energy for consumption

The maximum output energy for consumption ‘E’ at each route segment is computed by the product of the following two parameters shown in the equation.

Equation 33 $E = t * \sum_{i=1}^5 P$

Where;

t is the duration spent at each route segment.

$\sum_{i=1}^5 P$ is the sum of the maximum output power by the cells at each route segment.

2.8 Total energy

The total energy for consumption ‘T’ is the sum of the energy generated at each route segment.

Equation 34 $T = \sum_{i=1}^n E$

The models were tested for different routes and different dates. The Global model and the local model were compared whenever similar routes were available. Computation time is also measured for each forecast.

Results

The AcrMap toolbar ‘Solarcast’ was developed using a Python program to compute the results with a graphical user interface (GUI). Figure 1 shows the ArcMap interface with its basic elements and the Solarcast toolbar. It can receive inputs, such as from, to, speed, date, and time of the planned travel from the user. Figure 2 shows the outputs of the tool. It creates a shapefile with segment-wise attributes for the calculation. The duration, distance and total energy is computed and presented on the python console.

Fig. 1: Solarcast toolbar on ArcMap

Fig. 2: Numerical and graphical output of the tool (population is a background layer)

Table 3 shows the forecasted total energy production by the model solar-powered vehicle through the global model. Trials were executed for predefined cities.

Start			Destination	Speed (kM/h)	Precision (Computing time)	Computation		
Place	Date 2019	Time				Distance (kM)	Duration (Hour)	Energy (kWh)
Colombo (6.93194° N, 79.84555° E)	14/ 05	10:15	Jaffna (9.65876° N, 80.01899° E)	50	Moderate (65s)	391.7	7.67	2.69
								2.82
	15/ 05	08:15						3.52
								3.47

					High (77s)			3.4
					Low (70s)			3.58
London (51.50642° N, -0.12721° E)	13/ 05	10:30	Birmingham (52.47867° N, -1.90848° E)	65	High	253.6	3.82	1.45
Wuhan (30.64353° N, 114.32472° E)	16/ 05	09:30	Nanchang (28.68507° N, 115.89531° E)	70	High	377.5	5.28	2.52

Table 3. Energy forecast for sample locations, dates, times, speeds and precisions (Precision is provided internally for testing)

Table 4 shows the comparison between the forecast energy production using the global model and the local model by the model solar-powered vehicle.

Precision	Global Model				Local Model			
	Compu ting time	Distance (km)	Duration (Minutes)	Energy (Wh)	Compu ting time	Distance (km)	Duration (Minutes)	Energy (Wh)
Very High	36	1.63	1.77	29.9	122	1.62	1.76	25.0
High	16			30.1	67			24.9
Moderate	6			31.2	26			19.6
Low	6			31.0	26			19.6

Table 4. Energy forecast comparison on route place- 1 (7.222612°N, 79.866930°E) to Place 2 (7.223896°N, 79.881217°E) on 14/05/2019 at 09:45 at 65km/h

Figure 3 shows the graphs of influence of the time of start of the journey to the total energy production.

a

b

Fig. 3: Influence of the time of start to the total energy **a**. From Colombo to Jaffna on 15th May 2019, 6.00am to 6.00pm in each hour. **b** From Colombo to Jaffna on 15th May 2019 - 7.30am to 9.30am in each 15 minutes. The graph in Figure 3a shows the maximum energy production can be obtained by starting the trip at 8.00am or 9.00am on the given day during the given trip. When it is observed in a higher scale, the graph in figure 1b shows the maximum energy production occurs if the travel started at 8.30am.

a

b

Fig. 4: Influence of the date of travelling to the total energy. **a**. From Colombo to Jaffna at 08:30am each day. **b**. From Colombo to Jaffna at 09:30am each day.

The graph in figure 4a shows the maximum energy production that can be obtained on 16th May 2019 if the journey starts at 8.30am. If the journey starts at 9.30am, the maximum energy production can be obtained by travelling on 14th May 2019 by referring to the graph in figure 2b

Fig. 5: Variation of total solar irradiance perpendicular on sun rays for cloudless sky on a horizontal surface over the distance from the start of the travel.

The unusual deviations of total solar irradiance on the graph in figure 5 occurs due to the sudden changes on the temperature (figure 6a), pressure (figure 6b) and the humidity (figure 6c) values which are obtained by weather forecast.

Fig. 6. Variations of **a.** Temperature (K), **b.** Pressure (hPa), and **c.** Humidity (%) over the distance from the start of the travel (km).

Fig. 7: A sample of variation of the effective irradiance on the surface of the PV cells (mounted on the rooftop of the vehicle; from 300th to 400th segment).

The rapid variation of the effective irradiance on the surface of the PV cells (figure 7) occurs due to the angle of incidence of the solar rays which varies from 0° to 180°. If the sun is behind the PV surface, the angle of incidence is greater than 90° and the direct component of the solar irradiance does not contribute to the total irradiance.

Conclusions

The study has shown the ability of forecasting the energy production of a solar-powered vehicle travelling anywhere in the globe. The forecast is more accurate when the surface elevation data is available. But it takes a long processing time to determine the visibility of the sun. The global model has shown around 80% accuracy and 25% processing time when compared to the local model. The overall accuracy of both models depend on the accuracy of the weather forecast. Therefore, it is advantageous to use the global model instead of the local model with highly accurate data.

The maximum average energy generated for a 100km travel is about 1kWh for the tested routes in a given time. The average energy consumption of the model solar vehicle is 14kWh for a 100km. Therefore, solar energy contributes about 7% to the consumption.

This study was carried out based on the findings published on previous studies, the methods of which have not been validated for non-stationary solar panels. In order to validate the computations expressed in this paper, further experiments are needed to be carried out with a solar-powered vehicle or a vehicle fixed with solar panels.

It is proposed for the navigation services to include an ‘optimal route calculation extension’ for solar-powered vehicles. It is also proposed to further develop the model to suggest optimal dates and times for a given journey.

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